

Phonological Domains Questionnaire: KHOEKHOE

(by Kristine Feb 2005)

4/05

I. Language Profile

Alternative name: Nama
Variety: spoken in the Richtersveld area, South Africa

Number of speakers (language):

Number of speakers (dialect):

Language status (in Namibia):

Language prospects (in Namibia):

Language status (in the Richtersveld area):

everybody is bilingual (also old people); people from middle age upwards use Khoekhoe as first language; most of the younger people speak Afrikaans as first language, some hardly speak Khoekhoe at all

Language prospects (in the Richtersveld area):

recently introduced as second (or third?) language in school (first language Afrikaans); many children and youngsters do not speak the language anymore

Structural results: ???

II. Morpheme Types

(a) inflectional/derivational morpheme types

suffix

prosodic (?)

(suprasegmental?)

enclitic

(proclitic?)
stem position???
particle

III. Syllable

Possible syllable types:

CV
CVC
CVV
CVVC

- In CVV the vowels can be a long vowel (nasal or non-nasal) or a vowel combination/diphthong (not all combinations are possible)
- a monosyllabic form can be a free form - yes! -----examples!!!
- can a monomoraic form be a free form - not clear! (maybe they are clitics?!)-----examples!!!

I. Language profile		
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Language prospects (in Namibia):		
Language status (in the Richtersveld area):	everybody is bilingual (also old people); people from middle age upwards use Khoekhoe as first language; most of the younger people speak Afrikaans as first language, some hardly speak Khoekhoe at all	
Language prospects (in the Richtersveld area):	recently introduced as second (or third?) language in school (first language Afrikaans); many children and youngsters do not speak the language anymore	
Structural results (in Richtersveld):	heavy borrowing from Afrikaans, ...???	
II. Morpheme Types		
inflectional/derivational morpheme types	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - suffix - prosodic (?) - (suprasegmental?) - enclitic - (proclitic?) - stem position ??? - particle 	
III. Syllable		
Possible syllable types:	CV CVC (in CVCV-C) CVN CVV CVVC CVNC (e.g. lʔon-s “name-3FS”)	

in CVV the vowels can be	a long vowel (nasal or non-nasal)	aa, ee, ii, oo, uu ãã, ãĩ, ãũ note: õõ and êê do not exist!
	or a vowel combination / diphthong (not all combinations are possible)	ai, ae, au, ao, oe, oa, ui ãĩ, ãũ, õã, ãĩ note: ãê, ãõ, õê do not exist! (note also non-nasal combinations which do not occur!)

<p>a monosyllabic unit</p>	<p>can be a free form</p>	<p>long vowels (diphthongs equivalent) CVV(C):</p> <p><u>nouns:</u> lhũũ-p "white.person-3MS" (check where in data!)</p> <p><u>verbs:</u> ʔaa "drink" (in SethMinPairs)</p> <p><u>adjectives:</u> ʔexist?</p> <p><u>indep. Pronouns:</u> saa-s "2S-F(?)" (in SethMinPairs)</p> <p><u>postpositions:</u> !naa "that" (in SethMinPairs)</p> <p><u>others – (particles):</u> ñĩĩ FUT</p>
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short vowels CV(N):

nouns:

lʔon-s

“name-3FS”

verbs:

lom

“suck, zip”

adjectives: ?exist?

→ always with final nasal! (all in SethMinPairs)

<p>can a monomoraic form be a free form?</p>	<p>Yes?!</p>	<p><u>others – particles monomoraic:</u></p> <p>kie</p> <p>“DECL”</p> <p>kie</p> <p>“REMPST”</p> <p>ko</p> <p>“RECPST”</p> <p>ra / ta</p> <p>“IPFV”</p> <p>ka</p> <p>“indef.tense”</p> <p>kxa</p> <p>“QUEST”</p> <p>re</p> <p>“IMP/HORT”</p> <p>ti</p> <p>“QUOT”</p> <p>ti</p> <p>“ASSOC”</p> <p>?a</p> <p>“PRES.COP”</p> <p>?a</p> <p>“IMP/HORT-CONJ – that”</p> <p>→ never begin with click!</p> <p>(look for examples in data!)</p>
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vowel-initial or vowel only word?	<p>No! In apparently vowel initial words always glottal stop as onset;</p> <p>(There are suffixes that begin with a glottal stop where the glottal stop is not pronounced in fast speech)</p>	(examples)
Monomorphemic and polysyllabic forms - differences in phonological patterns (phonotactics)		
Phonotactic pattern - vowels	<p>→ lexical roots.</p> <p>There are phonotactic restrictions on the different positions within a root;</p> <p>A few grammatical morphemes like “<i>xaβe</i>” but Nouns, verbs and adjectives behave the same.</p>	<p>Restrictions on the occurrence of vowels in lexical stems (with examples):</p> <p>i. first vowel in a CVCV stem <i>a, o, u</i> (never nasal) <i>o</i> occurs as first vowel in CVCV only if the second vowel is <i>e</i>; <i>a</i> or <i>o</i> (rarely <i>i</i>), and <i>u</i> occurs only if the second vowel is <i>i</i> or <i>u</i>.</p> <p>ii. second vowel in a CVCV stem <i>i, e, a, o, u</i> (never nasal)</p>
Phonotactic pattern - consonants	<p>→lexical roots.</p> <p>There are phonotactic restrictions on the different positions within a root;</p> <p>Nouns, verbs and adjectives behave the same. Clicks occur only initially and only in lexical roots, apart from PP’s (are they perhaps lexical?)</p>	<p>Possible consonant occurrences in lexical roots:</p> <p>i. root-initial: any click or non-click consonant except <i>r</i>; <i>k</i> stands only before <i>a, o, u</i> and their nasal cognates and <i>ə</i> (; in particles, it may occur before <i>e</i> as well, e.g</p>

in the declarative marker *ke* and the past tense marker *ke* which differ only in tone. In these cases, the *k* is strongly palatalized). Usually *k* occurs only initially with a possible exception:

haka “four”; also *kx* never occurs before the front vowels

i, ĩ or *e*.

ii. medial (*C*₂ in *C*₁*V**C*₂*V*-roots):

p, x, m, n, r The occurrence of *m* is restricted in that it may generally not occur before *e, o* and *u* (though there are exceptions,

e.g. *mũũ* “(to) see”); *n* does not occur before *e* and *o* (though it does in the demonstrative *nee* “this”). In intervocalic position, e.g. medially in a stem, *p* through lenition is often pronounced as bilabial approximant [β].

iii. final (*N* in *CVN*):

m or *n* (Nasal CVV in very few cases surface

		<p>phonetically with an oral vowel and a final velar nasal (e.g. !ũũ “go” surfaces as [!uŋ]).</p> <p><i>n</i> is normally preceded by <i>a</i> or <i>o</i>.</p>
Variations across lexical categories (N,A,V)	None.	
Superheavy syllables	<p>CVVC - but this is bimoraic!</p> <p>→ always bimoraic roots followed by a consonantal enclitic</p>	<p>nee-s “this-3FS”</p> <p>nee-p “this-3MS”</p> <p>saa-s “2MorFS-2FS”</p> <p>lõã-s “girl-3FS” (in SethMinpairs)</p> <p>saa-ts</p> <p>lhũũ-s</p> <p>lhũũ-s</p>

		?ao-p ?ao-s (tsii-s tsii-p tsii-ts?) explain!!!
IV. Tone and Stress (Hagman)		
Domains Polymorphemic forms		
Changes affecting only tones (Hagman 77)	(a) <u>Compound noun roots(2 simple roots):</u> First root unchanged, in the second the tones of both morae become slightly lowered mid tones (assumed there were 3 tones)	
	(b) <u>Compound Verb roots (2 simple verb roots): (SVCs?!)</u> both tones of first root lowered slightly, both tones of the second raised slightly	
	(c) <u>reduplicated verb roots (redupl simple verb or adj root) CAUSATIVE:</u> tones of the second member become slightly lowered mid tones	Check in data!
	(d) <u>reduplicated verb roots before –sa (adj-deriving suffix):</u> if reduplicated verb root occurs before –sa, it acquires the same tonal alterations as a compound verb root	
	(e) <u>initial NPa□ in an interrogative sentence:</u> The “subordinative marker”(also MPP) –a□ of an initial NP in an interrog sentence has its tone raised from low to mid - may be considered part of interrogative intonation!	Check in data!
	(f) <u>The imperative hortative Negative ta□a□ :</u>	

	<p>the negative morpheme ta□a□ which may occur before the predicate phrase of an imperative-hortative sentence lowers all of the tones in any word which may happen to follow it by about one tone</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - intonation? - down step? 	
Secondary stress	(no!?)	
domains for stress (Dynamic stress = variation in loudness and quantity, not phonemic)	<p>Word stress: within a word that contains at least two morae, e.g. one root, the first mora is the most highly stressed then the stress decreases; suffixes always have a low degree of stress.</p>	
domains for tone	<p>Roots:</p> <p>6 possible tone combinations in a root: HH, HM, MH, MM, LH, LM (2 exceptions to this pattern)</p> <p>distribution classes with this form are: N root, V root, simple A, simple Number, simple ASSOC, DEM, UNIV, PRON, PP, FUT, NEG, PAST COP, CONJ, Clause relator (+ a few suffixes)</p>	
	<p>Particles and suffixes/ clitics: max. 1 mora</p> <p>???</p>	

	(PGN + subordinate suffix à)	
domains for intonation (phrase, clause, S, utterance)	<p>Clause, ???</p> <p>Sentence stress: Equally affects all of the morae upon which the sentence stress falls; greatest on lexical words; all possible words divided into 4 “stress classes” according to amount of sentence stress:</p> <p>Class 1: all words which may contain more than one morpheme (N, V, A, Num, Adv)</p> <p>Class 2: simple associative, demonstrative, universal, pronominal, postposition, perfective and negative</p> <p>Class3: conj, clause relator, past copula, fut tense</p> <p>Class4: all distribution classes filled by particles</p>	
“specialized” instances of stress & grammatical domains included (e.g. emphatic stress)	<p>Contrastive stress: Raises all the tones contained in the word upon which it falls! (rarely used); only words of stress class 1 and 2</p>	
V. Other Non-concatenative Processes ???		
Vowel harmony + tone spread	→ between the tense particles ké (PST), kò(prox PST) kà(indef tense) and the following imperfective aspect particle ta/ra	<p>kè + ra → kèrè</p> <p>kò + ra → kòrò</p> <p>kà + ra → kàrà</p>

	PGN-suffixes + “subordinative” -à	<p>-ta + -à → -tà</p> <p>-kxò + -à → -kxò</p> <p>-kxà + -à → -kxà</p> <p>-ke + -à → -kè</p> <p>-ko + -à → -kò</p> <p>-rò + -à → -rò</p> <p>-rà + -à → -rà</p> <p>-se + -à → -sè</p> <p>-so + -à → -sò</p> <p>-tà + -à → -tà</p> <p>if first vowel is high, the vowel sequence reduces to the corresponding mid vowel:</p> <p>-ti + -à → tè</p> <p>-tù + -à → tò</p> <p>-ʔi + -à → ʔè</p> <p>Ausnahme :</p> <p>-ku + -à → -kuà or more often -kà</p> <p>when -à follows the -i allomorph of the 3rd person masc. sing, the -I is dropped entirely</p>
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VI. “Free” Grammatical Morphemes

(possibly strange or different degree of phonology between stem morphemes and “less cohering” grammatical morphemes (stem-clitic-combinations, affix clusters))

Syllable structure	CVV(C) root-like particles (see above!) CV particles proper (?)	
Phonotactic variations	Proper particles never start with clicks! Otherwise all consonants allowed	
Tone (,stress)	Tense particles all Low tone except the future particle nĩí; all tones occur in particles	
Variations across morpheme types	1) Vowel harmony between the tense particles ké (PST), kò(prox PST) kà(indef tense) and the following imperfective aspect particle ta/ra See above! 2) PGN-suffixes and subordinate suffixes see above! 3) phonological allomorphs of the IPFV particle ta: ta / C##_ ra / V##_ depending on the last segment of the preceding word!	

	4) the initial glottal stop of the indef gender (indef common)suffix -ʔi totally assimilates to a preceding nasal; the nasal that precedes it stays moraic!	
VII. Polymorphemic Stem forms (exclude lexical allomorphy!) ???		
- Compound noun roots - Compound verb roots - Reduplicated verb roots (incl.adj) - Reduplicated verb roots before adj deriving suffix -sa see above!		
“Derived noun root”	N-si (N derived from adjective)	
Compound noun root	Verb root/noun root or adj + noun root See above!	
Derived adjective	Noun root/verb root + adj deriving suffix, e.g. -xà “attributive” -ʔo “privative” (=lacking/having a tendency not to)	Check -ʔo for nasal assimilation!!! No assimilation? (Hagman, p. 31)

	-sá “intrinsically ...ed” and so on!	
Compound post-position	Either both have the form of roots or only the second is a PP, the first one a noun	
Do all grammatical morphemes participate in the same way in the below processes?		
Phonotactics at and across morpheme boundaries		
Allophonic alternations at and across morpheme boundaries		
Shortening/lengthening at/across boundaries		
Assimilation/dissimilation/harmony at/across boundaries		
Place/manner/voicing/aspiration changes at/across boundaries		

Fortition/lenition at/across boundaries		
Tone/stress across or at different morph elements		
Insertion/deletion at/across boundaries		
Bipartite stems: discontinuous monomorphemic stem words		
VIII. Compounds, Concatenations, Juxtapositions		
Compounds	<p>(a) <u>Compound noun roots</u> (2 simple roots): First root unchanged, in the second the tones of both morae become slightly lowered mid tones (assumed there were 3 tones)</p> <p>(b) <u>Compound Verb roots</u> (2 simple verb roots): both tones of first root lowered slightly, both tones of the second raised slightly</p>	
How are they like/different from polymorphemic stem + gramm forms?	Tonal pattern	
Phonotactics at boundaries	Coda of first is the same as in free form: V or N	

	Onset of second is the same as in free form: Any consonant incl. Clicks	
Alternations, processes, other changes at boundaries (deletion/insertion/assimilation/dissimilation, place/manner/voicing changes etc.)	No (assimilatory or other) changes at boundary	
Tone/stress patterns in comparison to those seen in IV	1) Compound nouns: First root unchanged, in the second the tones of both morae become slightly lowered mid tones (assumed there were 3 tones) 2) compound verbs: both tones of first root lowered slightly, both tones of the second raised slightly	
Differences for differing compounding types	Tonal effects differ in verb and noun compounds: see above!	
IX. Reduplication		
Functions	1) V/ADJ-reduplication: CAUS Tones of second member all become slightly lowered middle tones!	

	2) V root-kaV root: Repetitive Same tone alterations	
What is copied? – is it always the same portion?	Simple root / simple ADJ	
Portion phonologically or morphologically specifiable?	Morphologically: root (always a foot)	
X. Phrase/Sentence-level phenomena check data !!!		
Intonation/prosody within and across phrases and clauses	The imperative-hortative negative táá which may occur before the predicate phrase of an imp-hort sentence, lowers all the tones in any word which may happen to follow it by about one tone	
	<u>Declarative sentence intonation</u> : 2 parts 1) general sentence intonation: also applies to interrogative sentences – sentence tends to decline from beginning to end (downdrift!)	

	<p>The decline may be incounteracted by a word which is affected by emphatic stress or interrogative intonation, but even then the rest of the sentence declines</p> <p>2) lowered final intonation:</p> <p>every declarative sentence has lowered final intonation, e.g. lowering by one tone of the last mora of the sentence (L becomes extra-L !) – Hagman: intonational, not morphotonemic (extra-L is phonetic)!</p>	
	<p><u>Interrogative sentence intonation:</u></p> <p>1) In the Initial NPà in an interrogative sentence the tone of the suffix is raised from L to M</p> <p>2) general sentence intonation: the pitch of the voice does not decline nearly as much, it is nearly level</p>	

	throughout; neither is there as much lowering of the final mora.	
Phrase-level stress	???	
Clause-level stress	???	
Sentence-level stress	<p>Sentence stress:</p> <p>Equally affects all of the morae upon which the sentence stress falls; greatest on lexical words; all possible words divided into 4 “stress classes” according to amount of sentence stress:</p> <p>Class 1: all words which may contain more than one morpheme (N, V, A, Num, Adv)</p> <p>Class 2: simple associative, demonstrative, universal, pronominal, postposition, perfective and negative</p> <p>Class3: conj, clause relator, past copula, fut tense</p> <p>Class4: all distribution classes filled by particles</p> <p>Contrastive stress:</p>	

	<p>Raises all the tones contained in the word upon which it falls! (rarely used); only words of stress class 1 and 2</p> <p>(compare above!)</p>	
Pause phenomena within and across these domains	<p>Pause after ke (DECL) And after each sentence</p>	
XI. other special things		
Distribution of and constraints on geminates	<p>the initial glottal stop of the indef gender (indef common)suffix -ʔi totally assimilates to a preceding nasal; the nasal that precedes it stays moraic! (see above!)</p>	
Evidence for the relevance of foot structure?	???	
Special exceptions to the above processes	???	
